

DATA NOTE

Physiologically relevant real-world light exposure and its behavioural and environmental determinants in Kumasi, Ghana

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved]

Gabriel Kwaku Agbeshie ¹, Isaiah Osei Duah Junior^{1,2},
Albert Kwadjo Amoah Andoh ¹,
Nana Akwasi Owusu Mensah ¹, Awurama Yenkuah Ampoma-Mensah¹,
Johannes Zauner ^{1,7}

¹Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ashanti Region, Ghana

²Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana, USA

³Galaxy Eye Care Limited, Kumasi, Ghana

⁴Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany

⁵Max Planck Institute for Biological Cybernetics, Tübingen, Germany

⁶TUMCREATE Ltd., Singapore, Singapore

⁷University of Oxford, Oxford, England, UK

V1 **First published:** 26 Sep 2025, 5:300
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21304.1>
Latest published: 26 Sep 2025, 5:300
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21304.1>

Abstract

Light plays a significant role in human physiology and behaviour, influencing sleep, mood, alertness and overall health. Yet light exposure remains a neglected determinant of health, with most evidence coming from high-income countries. This data note presents a dataset collected in Kumasi, Ghana, between October 2024 and February 2025, containing personal light exposure measured with wearable melanopic light loggers alongside behavioural and environmental factors obtained through self-reports. Fifteen participants (n=8 female, mean±SD age 22.6±1.2 years) wore three ActLumus light-logging devices continuously for seven days, recording light exposure every 10 seconds at the near-corneal plane, chest and wrist. Participants also completed daily questionnaires on sleep, mood and physical activity, as well as structured assessments of their sleep environment and light-related behaviours. This dataset provides the first high-resolution account of daily light exposure in sub-Saharan Africa. By enabling cross-context comparisons, it contributes to understanding the diversity of light environments globally and can inform interventions for sleep health, mental health and chronic

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 1 26 Sep 2025	 view	

1. **Julia Ribeiro da Silva Vallim** ,
Universidade Federal de São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil
2. **Angus Burns** , Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, USA
Harvard Medical School Department of Neurology (Ringgold ID: 207096), Boston, USA

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

disease prevention.

Plain language summary

Light affects how we sleep, feel and stay healthy. But most research on light exposure has been carried out in high-income countries, meaning we know very little about people's real-life light environments in other parts of the world. This study provides the first detailed dataset of daily light exposure in sub-Saharan Africa. Fifteen young adults in Kumasi, Ghana, wore small devices that measured the light around them every few seconds for one week, while also answering short questions about their sleep, mood and daily routines. The dataset shows how people in Ghana experience light in everyday life and allows comparisons with data from other countries. By making this resource openly available, we hope to support future research on how light exposure influences sleep, mental health and the risk of long-term diseases — helping to shape healthier light environments worldwide.

Keywords

personal light exposure, Africa, circadian rhythms, non-visual effects of light, wearables, wearable light loggers, light-related behaviour, sleep, chronobiology

This article is included in the [European](#)

[Association of National Metrology Institutes](#)
(EURAMET) gateway.

Corresponding authors: Manuel Spitschan (manuel.spitschan@tum.de), Kwadwo Owusu Akuffo (akuffokwadwoowusu@knust.edu.gh)

Author roles: **Agbeshie GK:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Duah Junior IO:** Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Andoh AKA:** Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ampong J:** Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Mensah NAO:** Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ampoma-Mensah AY:** Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Zauner J:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Spitschan M:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Akuffo KO:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: Competing interests M.S. declares the following potential conflicts of interest in the past five years (2021-2025). Academic roles: Member of the Board of Directors, Society of Light, Rhythms and Circadian Health (SLRCH); Chair of Joint Technical Committee 20 (JTC20) of the International Commission on Illumination (CIE); Member of the Daylight Academy; Chair of Research Data Alliance Working Group Optical Radiation and Visual Experience Data. Remunerated roles: Speaker of the Steering Committee of the Daylight Academy; Ad-hoc reviewer for the Health and Digital Executive Agency of the European Commission; Ad-hoc reviewer for the Swedish Research Council; Associate Editor for LEUKOS, journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society; Examiner, University of Manchester; Examiner, Flinders University; Examiner, University of Southern Norway. Funding: Received research funding and support from the Max Planck Society, Max Planck Foundation, Max Planck Innovation, Technical University of Munich, Wellcome Trust, National Research Foundation Singapore, European Partnership on Metrology, VELUX Foundation, Bayerisch-Tschechische Hochschulagentur (BTHA), BayFrance (Bayerisch-Französisches Hochschulzentrum), BayFOR (Bayerische Forschungsallianz) and Reality Labs Research. Honoraria for talks: Received honoraria from the ISGlobal, Research Foundation of the City University of New York and the Stadt Ebersberg, Museum Wald und Umwelt. Travel reimbursements: Daimler und Benz Stiftung. Patents: Named on European Patent Application EP23159999.4A ("System and method for corneal-plane physiologically-relevant light logging with an application to personalized light interventions related to health and well-being"). M.S. declares no influence of the disclosed roles or relationships on the work presented herein. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish or preparation of the manuscript. J.Z. declares the following potential conflicts of interest in the past five years (2021-2025). Academic roles: Member of Joint Technical Committee 20 (JTC20) of the International Commission on Illumination (CIE); Member of Research Data Alliance Working Group Optical Radiation and Visual Experience Data; Speaker of group 2 (melanopic effects of light) of the Technical Scientific Committee (TWA) of the German Society of Lighting Technology and Design (LiTG) Remunerated roles: Examiner, Swiss Lighting Society; Teacher, LiTG; Teacher, University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Teacher, Technical University of Applied Sciences, Rosenheim. Associated partner, 3lpi lighting design + engineering, Munich. Tool- and 3D-model design, Zumtobel Lighting GmbH; Course design, University of Applied Sciences, Munich & Virtual University Bavaria. Honoraria for talks: Received honoraria from LiTG; Lamilux (Heinrich Strunz GmbH); Robert-Bosch Hospital Stuttgart; Ergotopia GmbH; German statutory accident insurance institution for the administrative sector (VBG); BRIXEN CULTUR, Italy; KITEO GmbH & Co.KG; University of Applied Sciences Augsburg. Travel reimbursements: Daimler und Benz Stiftung. Patents: Together with 3lpi holds a design patent for non-visually optimized luminaire (No 008194021-0001 through -0006) at the European Union Intellectual property office. The remaining authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Grant information: The MeLiDos project (22NRM05 MeLiDos) received support from the "European Partnership on Metrology" with co-funding from the "European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme" and the participating member states. Additional funding was granted by the TUM Global Incentive Fund (GIF0000031) to promote collaboration between TUM and KNUST. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. M.S. is supported by a Max Planck Research Group from the Max Planck Society.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Agbeshie GK *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Agbeshie GK, Duah Junior IO, Andoh AKA *et al.* **Physiologically relevant real-world light exposure and its behavioural and environmental determinants in Kumasi, Ghana [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:300 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21304.1>

First published: 26 Sep 2025, 5:300 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21304.1>

Introduction

Light exposure is an important environmental factor that significantly influences human health and well-being¹. In addition to its central role in vision, light acts as the primary zeitgeber, synchronising the endogenous circadian rhythms with the natural light-dark cycle². However, the prevalence of artificial lighting and modern indoor lifestyles can disrupt this synchronization, leading to various health issues due to altered daily patterns of light exposure³⁻⁶. The non-visual effects of light involve specialized photoreceptors in the eye and are mainly mediated by the intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs), which are most sensitive to short-wavelength light^{7,8}.

Analysing real-world light exposure and related behaviours is key for a better understanding of and potential reduction in any negative health consequences arising from light at the ‘wrong’ time, while enhancing the acute and short-term benefits of light exposure, such as boosts in alertness and improved sleep quality. Although extensive laboratory research has characterised the effects of light under controlled conditions, these light stimuli rarely reflect the light exposures encountered under real-world conditions^{9,10}. Empirical studies of light exposure in daily life using wearable light loggers are essential for providing additional information about exposure patterns and their potential consequences for health.

Wearable light loggers and dosimeters have emerged as valuable tools for objectively measuring personal light exposure in real-world settings¹¹⁻¹⁴. These devices can capture spectral information across the visible range and output various light exposure metrics, including visual quantities (e.g. photopic illuminance) and non-visual quantities (e.g. alpha-opic irradiance, melanopic equivalent daylight illuminance, abbreviation as melanopic EDI)^{15,16}, which in turn can be aggregated into relevant summary metrics¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Objective measurements can be supplemented by subjective tools that capture light-exposure-related behaviours, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how individuals interact with their light environment²⁰.

Despite a growing interest in personal light exposure, more extensive data is needed from diverse populations and geographical locations to fully understand variability in light exposure patterns and their health implications. To date, most research has focused on populations in Europe or North America^{17,21}. First, comparisons with other regions of the world demonstrate the differences between countries, cultures and climate conditions, as a recent study on light exposure in Malaysia and Switzerland has shown²². Datasets from other regions are less common and even fewer are publicly available, which limits our ability to assess generalisability and identify population-specific factors that influence light exposure and its effects on human health. Light exposure data collected in Ghana provides an opportunity to study how different environmental conditions, cultural practices and daily routines correlate with the light exposure patterns. This contributes to a broader understanding of the diversity of human physiological responses to light, particularly within the African population.

This data note describes a dataset on personal light exposure collected in Ghana. The primary objective of the dataset was to characterize personal light exposure patterns in Ghana and investigate the real-world determinants of participant’s exposure. The use of a standardized, multi-site study protocol²³ ensures that the data are comparable with a growing number of other sites around the world including Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Turkey and Costa Rica. By making this dataset publicly available and adhering to the principles of FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data²⁴, we aim to contribute valuable information to the field, facilitating further research and the development of more personalised and effective interventions for optimising light exposure for health and well-being.

Methods

This dataset was collected in an observational field study in which participants were recruited in Kumasi, Ashanti Region, Ghana (coordinates 6.6750074282377385 N, -1.572643823555129 W), to evaluate their personal light exposure patterns using wearable light loggers and questionnaires following a standardized, multi-site protocol²³. This study was conducted within the framework of the Metrology for wearable light loggers and optical radiation dosimeters (MeLiDos) project that aims to quantify individual light exposure using wearable light loggers and solar UV dosimeters²⁵. For the general overview of this study, see [Figure 1](#).

Participant recruitment

Participants were recruited via advertisements disseminated as flyers on various social media platforms. Participants were directed to scan a QR code to access an online platform (Research Electronic Data Capture, or REDCap^{26,27}) on which they could complete the first screening survey. The aims of the study and detailed information were provided during this screening step. Eligible participants were aged 18–65 years, had no psychiatric or sleep disorder, were not using tobacco or recreational drugs or taking medication, had normal vision and were not using prescribed glasses and lived within a 60-km radius of the research centre. Eligible participants were sent a picture of a spectacle-mounted ActLumus light logger (Condor Instruments, São Paulo, Brazil) and were asked to confirm that they would feel comfortable wearing it throughout the study period. Participants received financial remuneration of €82.30 at the end of the study based on their compliance with the experimental light study, which required them to wear the light logger for at least 80% of their waking hours. 15 participants were recruited for the study.

Procedures

Eligible participants were invited to the department on a given Monday to begin the light exposure assessment and finished the following Monday. On the first Monday (day 1), participants received detailed information about the study and signed an informed consent form. They also received three wearable light loggers, which they were instructed to wear at chest level, at the near-corneal plane and on their wrist. They were given instructions on how to use the devices correctly. They also

Figure 1. Overview of the study design. **A**, Study location shown on map. **B**, Participants recording periods including implicit missing data in grey. Of note, the gap in between participant S011 and S012 is because of a week break during the data collection during the winter holiday period. **C**, Actual photoperiod duration in Kumasi, Ghana (pink). **D**, Average and recommended healthy daytime, evening and sleep light exposure (melanopic equivalent daylight illuminance, melanopic EDI).

installed the MyCap app²⁸, which integrates with REDCap and was used to complete the daily questionnaires during the light study.

Measures and data collection

ActLumus light loggers (Condor Instruments, São Paulo, Brazil)

Three ActLumus light loggers (Condor Instruments, São Paulo, Brazil) were used to objectively measure personal light exposure and activity at different locations. One ActLumus was positioned near the corneal plane on a 3D-printed holder attached to the bridge of a pair of non-prescription glasses. A second light logger was worn as a manufacturer-supplied pendant attached to a lanyard to measure light at chest level. The third light logger was worn at wrist level using the manufacturer-provided wristbands. The devices record across the visible spectrum and provide calibrated alpha-opic and photopic metrics, as well as movement using an integrated tri-axial accelerometer. Each light logger was set to a 10-second sampling interval to achieve highly temporally resolved data. Participants were also instructed to follow instructions about when to wear and remove them and how to document wear and non-wear. They were also informed to ensure that the light loggers were not obstructed by clothing and to remove them when in contact with water or during intense sporting activities. The devices were never charged or turned off during the light study week. The light exposure data were retrieved from the devices when they were returned on the final Monday (day 8) and stored on a secure, personal computer on campus.

Chronotype questionnaires

On the first day of the light exposure study, participants completed the chronotype questionnaire. This consisted of the Munich Chronotype Questionnaire (MCTQ)²⁹, which assesses circadian time using questions about sleep and wake habits during work and leisure periods and the Morning-Eveningness Questionnaire (MEQ)³⁰ to determine their circadian preference, i.e. the times of day at which they perform certain activities.

Visual Light Sensitivity Questionnaire-8 (VLSQ-8)

Participants completed the eight-point Visual Light Sensitivity Questionnaire (VLSQ-8)³¹ on the final day of the data collection week after returning the wearable devices. The questionnaire asked participants to estimate the frequency and severity of their photosensitivity, as well as its impact on their daily behaviours, using a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = “Never” to 5 = “Always”).

Morning sleep log

Participants completed the Sleep Diary every morning after waking up in order to assess their sleep timing, duration and quality. The questionnaire consisted of nine items, with the final item scored on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (“Very poor”) to 5 (“Very good”).

Ecological momentary assessment (“Current conditions”)

Participants completed a short questionnaire four times a day (at 11:00, 14:00, 17:00 and 20:00) about their current light

environment, mood and level of sleepiness. They received reminders via the REDCap/MyCap app and were instructed to set their own phone alarms to help them remember. For the light conditions section, participants selected one or two main light sources from a list of eight options based on a modified version of the Harvard Light Exposure Assessment Diary (H-LEA). Mood was measured using a shortened version of the Mood Zoom questionnaire³² and sleepiness was rated using a 10-point Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS)³³, which ranges from 1 (“Extremely alert”) to 10 (“Extremely sleepy, fighting sleep”).

Exercise log

Each evening before going to bed, the participants completed a custom-made questionnaire about their daily physical activity. The questionnaire collected information on the intensity of the exercise (vigorous, moderate or light), where it took place (indoors or outdoors) and how much time was spent sitting or lying down during the day.

Wellbeing log

Each evening before going to sleep, the participants completed a modified version of the WHO-5 Wellbeing Index³⁴. This comprised five statements about their mood, energy levels, sleep quality and interest in daily life. For four of the statements, participants rated how often they experienced positive emotions using a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 0 (“Never”) to 5 (“Always”). For the question about sleep quality, they rated it from 1 (“Very poor”) to 5 (“Very good”).

Light exposure and activity log

Each evening, the participants completed the modified Harvard Light Exposure Assessment (H-LEA³⁵), which was provided during their first visit to the office (on day 1). For each hour of the day, they recorded the main light source to which they were exposed, defined as the ‘biggest and brightest light source’, as well as the activity in which they were engaged during that hour. Light sources were chosen from eight predefined categories, including indoor and outdoor electric light, daylight indoors or outdoors, screen-based light, darkness and light during sleep. If they were exposed to multiple light sources within the same hour, participants selected from a list of combined options. Activities were selected from eight categories, such as sleeping, working, commuting or spending time outdoors. To ensure compliance, participants submitted a photo of the completed form each morning to a personal shared folder on Google Drive. They also used the MyCap app to rate their confidence in the accuracy of their responses on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (“Not confident at all”) to 5 (“Completely confident”).

Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment (LEBA)

At the end of the study (on day 8), the participants completed the Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment (LEBA²⁰), which is a 22-item questionnaire designed to assess light-related behaviours retrospectively during the light study week. The first three items, relating to the use of blue-filtering, orange-tinted, or red-tinted glasses, were excluded as these were not relevant due to the participants wearing light loggers. The final version included 19 items focusing on behaviours such as daylight exposure,

smartphone use, bedtime light habits and electric light use at home. Participants rated how often they engaged in these behaviours using a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (“Never”) to 5 (“Always”).

Assessment of Sleep Environment (ASE) questionnaire

On the final day (day 8), participants completed the 13-item Assessment of Sleep Environment (ASE³⁶) questionnaire, which asked about factors in their sleeping environment, such as light, noise, temperature and humidity, that could influence sleep quality or affect light measurements from the light logger placed near them during sleep (e.g. light entering through windows). They rated their agreement with each statement on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

Data processing and availability

The data collected in REDCap was exported as a comma-separated (CSV) file and processed using Microsoft Excel 2016. To anonymise the data, each participant was given a unique identifier ranging from KNUST_S001 to KNUST_S015 and the position of the light logger was labelled as “w” for the wrist, “c” for the chest and “h” for the head. This dataset is publicly available on Zenodo under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15576732>³⁷. While the repository contains the raw (anonymized) data at start, it will be augmented into a standard format at a later point. This augmentation includes the addition of metadata in a human- and machine-readable format as well as the correction and documentation of implausible entries by participants (e.g., mixing up AM and PM when entering times so that typical sequences like going to bed, sleeping, waking up, getting up, do not fall on a continuous timeline). All steps will be archived on Zenodo and assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) for full traceability. All data are available under the terms of the CC-BY 4.0 Attribution.

Dataset description

The dataset is organised into two main categories: Group (containing files for all participants) and Individual (containing participant-specific files and logs). Each participant is identified by a unique participant ID (PID). The study was carried out over seven days for each participant (eight calendar dates), with data collected using continuous wearable light loggers (ActLumus) and standardised questionnaires in RedCap via the MyCap mobile app.

Group-level folder

This folder contains structured data to facilitate import during data analysis (see [Table 1](#)).

Individual-level folder

This contains the 15 participants’ folders with subfolders named by domain. The individual files reflect the data collection schedule and instruments used (See [Table 2](#)).

Abbreviations

MCTQ: Munich Chronotype Questionnaire

MEQ: Morningness - Eveningness Questionnaire

Table 1. Description of group-level folders.

Folder Name	Description
Chronotype	Four CSV files: one for the Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire (MEQ), another for the Munich Chronotype Questionnaire (MCTQ), lookup tables for MEQ and MCTQ, each containing N = 15 responses
Demographics	Two CSV files: one with demographics data only and another with lookup table for all participants.
Discharge	Two CSV files: one containing responses to five post-study questionnaires: LEBA, ASE, VLSQ-8, mTFA and general feedback; the other with lookup table for 15 participants
Screening	Two CSV files: one with both demographics and health screening data for all participants and demographics and health screening lookup table.

LEBA, Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment; ASE, Assessment of Sleep Environment; VLSQ-8, Visual Light Sensitivity Questionnaire-8; mTFA, Modified Theory Framework of Acceptability

Table 2. Description of individual-level folder.

Subfolder	Filename	Description
chronotype/	PID_mctq_yyyymmdd.csv / PID_meq_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains two CSV files: one for MEQ and the other for MCTQ chronotype questionnaires completed on Day 1 of light study (Monday)
continuous/actlumus_chest/	PID_c_actlumus_Log_timestamp.txt	Contains two CSV files: one for light exposure (10s intervals, 7 days) and the other an automated report
continuous/actlumus_head/	PID_h_actlumus_Log_timestamp.txt	Contains two CSV files: one for light exposure (10s intervals, 7 days) and the other an automated report
continuous/actlumus_wrist/	PID_w_actlumus_Log_timestamp.txt	Contains two CSV files: one for light exposure (10s intervals, 7 days) and the other an automated report
continuous/currentconditions/	PID_currentconditions_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: EMA on mood (MoodZoom), light and alertness (Karolinska Sleepiness Scale); 4x daily
continuous/exercisediary/	PID_exercisediary_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Evening exercise log
continuous/experiencelog/	PID_experiencelog_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Self-reports of experiences wearing light loggers
continuous/mHLEA_digital/	PID_mHLEA_digital_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Daily digital subjective light exposure reports
continuous/mHLEA_paper/	PID_mHLEA_paper_yyyymmdd.xlsx	Contains one Excel file: Transcribed paper version of mHLEA
continuous/sleepdiary/	PID_sleepdiary_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Morning sleep log
continuous/wearlog/	PID_wearlog_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Light logger wear/removal events
continuous/wellbeingdiary/	PID_wellbeingdiary_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Evening well-being rating
demographics/	PID_demog_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Pre-study screening data completed online to gather informations about participants' age, sex, employment status, etc.
screening/	PID_screening_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains one CSV file: Informations about participants' lifestyle and health
discharge/	PID_ASE_yyyymmdd.csv, PID_feedback_yyyymmdd.csv, PID_LEBA_yyyymmdd.csv, PID_mTFA_yyyymmdd.csv, PID_VLSQ8_yyyymmdd.csv	Contains five CSV files: Post-study assessments (ASE, LEBA, VLSQ-8, Feedback, mTFA), completed on Day 8

EMA, Ecological Momentary Assessment; mHLEA, Modified Harvard Light Exposure Assessment

mH-LEA: Modified Harvard Light Exposure Assessment

LEBA: Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment

VLSQ-8: Visual Light Sensitivity Questionnaire

ASE: Assessment of Sleep Environment

mTFA: Modified Theory Framework of Acceptability

EMA: Ecological Momentary Assessment

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (data principles)

KNUST: Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology

ID: Identification

Statements

Ethical approval

The multi-site study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Medical Ethics Committee of the Technical University of Munich (2024-118-S-SB). Locally, the study protocol was formally approved by the Committee on Human Research, Publication and Ethics at the School of Medicine and Dentistry, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana (CHRPE/AP/644/24). Participants provided written informed consent, confirming their voluntary involvement in the research and their right to withdraw at any time, after the aims and approaches to be employed in the study had been thoroughly explained to them. All investigative procedures were performed in strict adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki.

Author contributions

Conceptualisation: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Data curation: GKA, JZ, KOA

Formal analysis: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Funding acquisition: MS, KOA

Investigation: GKA, MS, KOA

Methodology: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Project administration: GKA, KOA

Resources: GKA, IODJ, AKAA, JA, NAOM, AYAM, MS, KOA

Software: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Supervision: JZ, MS, KOA

Validation: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Visualisation: GKA, JZ, MS, KOA

Writing – original draft preparation: GKA, IODJ, AKAA, JA, NAOM, AYAM, KOA

Writing – review & editing: GKA, IODJ, AKAA, JA, NAOM, AYAM, JZ, MS, KOA

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express gratitude to the participants who volunteered in this study, as well as Dr. Samson Darrah and Dr. Eldrick Adu Acquah for their unwavering technical assistance and support during the ethics application.

References

- Brown TM, Brainard GC, Cajochen C, *et al.*: **Recommendations for daytime, evening, and nighttime indoor light exposure to best support physiology, sleep, and wakefulness in healthy adults.** *PLoS Biol.* 2022; **20**(3): e3001571. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Blume C, Garbaza C, Spitschan M: **Effects of light on human circadian rhythms, sleep and mood.** *Somnologie (Berl).* 2019; **23**(3): 147–156. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Burns AC, Saxena R, Vetter C, *et al.*: **Time spent in outdoor light is associated with mood, sleep, and circadian rhythm-related outcomes: a cross-sectional and longitudinal study in over 400,000 UK Biobank participants.** *J Affect Disord.* 2021; **295**: 347–352. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Burns AC, Windred DP, Rutter MK, *et al.*: **Day and night light exposure are associated with psychiatric disorders: an objective light study in >85,000 people.** *Nat Ment Health.* 2023; **1**(11): 853–862. [Reference Source](#)
- Windred DP, Burns AC, Lane JM, *et al.*: **Brighter nights and darker days predict higher mortality risk: a prospective analysis of personal light exposure in >88,000 individuals.** *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2024; **121**(43): e2405924121. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Windred DP, Burns AC, Rutter MK, *et al.*: **Personal light exposure patterns and incidence of type 2 diabetes: analysis of 13 million hours of light sensor data and 670,000 person-years of prospective observation.** *Lancet Reg Health Eur.* 2024; **42**: 100943. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Spitschan M: **Melanopsin contributions to non-visual and visual function.** *Curr Opin Behav Sci.* 2019; **30**: 67–72. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Lucas RJ, Peirson SN, Berson DM, *et al.*: **Measuring and using light in the melanopsin age.** *Trends Neurosci.* 2014; **37**(1): 1–9. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Webler FS, Spitschan M, Foster RG, *et al.*: **What is the 'spectral diet' of humans?** *Curr Opin Behav Sci.* 2019; **30**: 80–86. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Spitschan M: **Time-varying light exposure in chronobiology and sleep research experiments.** *Front Neurol.* 2021; **12**: 654158. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- van Duijnhoven J, Hartmeyer SL, Didikoglu A, *et al.*: **Measuring light exposure in daily life: a review of wearable light loggers.** *Build Environ.* 2025; **274**: 112771. [Publisher Full Text](#)

12. Hartmeyer SL, Weblor FS, Andersen M: **Towards a framework for light-dosimetry studies: methodological considerations.** *Light Res Technol.* 2022; **55**(4-5): 377-399.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
13. Spitschan M, Smolders K, Vandendriessche B, et al.: **Verification, analytical validation and clinical validation (V3) of wearable dosimeters and light loggers.** *Digit Health.* 2022; **8**: 20552076221144858.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
14. Price LL, Lyachev A, Khazova M: **Optical performance characterization of light-logging actigraphy dosimeters.** *J Opt Soc Am A Opt Image Sci Vis.* 2017; **34**(4): 545-557.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
15. Price LLA, Blattner P: **Circadian and visual photometry.** *Prog Brain Res.* 2022; **273**(1): 1-11.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
16. Schlangen LJM, Price LLA: **The lighting environment, its metrology, and non-visual responses.** *Front Neurol.* 2021; **12**: 624861.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
17. Hartmeyer SL, Andersen M: **Towards a framework for light-dosimetry studies: quantification metrics.** *Light Res Technol.* 2023; **56**(4): 337-365.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
18. Hammad G, Wulff K, Skene DJ, et al.: **Open-source python module for the analysis of personalized light exposure data from wearable light loggers and dosimeters.** *Leukos.* 2024; **20**(4): 380-389.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
19. Zauner J, Hartmeyer S, Spitschan M: **LightLogR: reproducible analysis of personal light exposure data.** *J Open Source Softw.* 2025; **10**(107): 7601.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
20. Siraji MA, Lazar RR, van Duijnhoven J, et al.: **An inventory of human light exposure behaviour.** *Sci Rep.* 2023; **13**(1): 22151.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
21. Smolders K: **Opinion: the need for intensive longitudinal data to advance translational research in the domain of light and health.** *Light Res Technol.* 2024; **56**(2): 110-112.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
22. Biller AM, Zauner J, Cajochen C, et al.: **Physiologically-relevant light exposure and light behaviour in Switzerland and Malaysia.** *bioRxiv.* 2025; 2025.01.07.631760.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
23. Guidolin C, Aerts S, Agbeshie GK, et al.: **Protocol for a prospective, multicentre, cross-sectional cohort study to assess personal light exposure.** *BMC Public Health.* 2024; **24**(1): 3285.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
24. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg JJ, et al.: **The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship.** *Sci Data.* 2016; **3**: 160018.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
25. Spitschan M, Zauner J, Tengelin MN, et al.: **Illuminating the future of wearable light metrology: overview of the MeLiDos project.** *Measurement.* 2024; **235**: 114909.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
26. Harris PA, Taylor R, Thielke R, et al.: **Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap)—a metadata-driven methodology and workflow process for providing translational research informatics support.** *J Biomed Inform.* 2009; **42**(2): 377-381.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
27. Harris PA, Taylor R, Minor BL, et al.: **The REDCap consortium: building an international community of software platform partners.** *J Biomed Inform.* 2019; **95**: 103208.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
28. Harris PA, Swafford J, Serdoz ES, et al.: **MyCap: a flexible and configurable platform for mobilizing the participant voice.** *JAMIA Open.* 2022; **5**(2): ooac047.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
29. Zavada A, Gordijn MCM, Beersma DGM, et al.: **Comparison of the munich chronotype questionnaire with the Horne-Östberg's morningness-eveningness score.** *Chronobiol Int.* 2005; **22**(2): 267-78.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
30. Horne JA, Ostberg O: **A self-assessment questionnaire to determine morningness-eveningness in human circadian rhythms.** *Int J Chronobiol.* 1976; **4**(2): 97-110.
[PubMed Abstract](#)
31. Verriotto JD, Gonzalez A, Aguilar MC, et al.: **New methods for quantification of visual photosensitivity threshold and symptoms.** *Transl Vis Sci Technol.* 2017; **6**(4): 18.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
32. Tsanas A, Saunders KEA, Bilderbeck AC, et al.: **Daily longitudinal self-monitoring of mood variability in bipolar disorder and borderline personality disorder.** *J Affect Disord.* 2016; **205**: 225-233.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
33. Akerstedt T, Gillberg M: **Subjective and objective sleepiness in the active individual.** *Int J Neurosci.* 1990; **52**(1-2): 29-37.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
34. Bech P: **Measuring the dimensions of psychological general well-being by the WHO-5.** *QoL Newsletter.* 2004; **32**: 15-16.
[Reference Source](#)
35. Bajaj A, Rosner B, Lockley SW, et al.: **Validation of a light questionnaire with real-life photopic illuminance measurements: the harvard light exposure assessment questionnaire.** *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2011; **20**(7): 1341-9.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
36. Grandner MA, Valencia DY, Seixas AA, et al.: **Development and initial validation of the Assessment of Sleep Environment (ASE): describing and quantifying the impact of subjective environmental factors on sleep.** *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022; **19**(20): 13599.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
37. Akuffo KO, Agbeshie GK, Zauner J, et al.: **Personal light exposure dataset for Kumasi, Ghana.** 2025.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 14 October 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23041.r61406>

© 2025 Burns A. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Angus Burns

¹ Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA, USA

² Harvard Medical School Department of Neurology (Ringgold ID: 207096), Boston, Massachusetts, USA

This work presents a well-designed and timely open dataset characterizing real-world light exposure patterns among young adults in Kumasi, Ghana. This work proposes to be the first account of its kind, measuring light exposure in free-living human beings under naturalistic conditions from sub-Saharan Africa. Using three ActLumus light loggers placed near the corneal plane, chest, and wrist, participants' light exposure was recorded (seven days continuous). Participants provided self-reported measures of sleep, mood, exercise, and light-related behaviors. By integrating objective, high-frequency light data with ecological momentary assessments and validated questionnaires (e.g., MEQ, MCTQ, WHO-5), the dataset enables sophisticated analyses of light, mood and behavior relationships under naturalistic conditions. Small methodological reporting issues are raised below. Further expansion of this dataset to a more demographically diverse population and simply a larger sample will dramatically improve its value.

The study's strengths lie in the novelty of its sample, rigorous methodology for light measurement and commitment to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. The open-source repository structure fosters reproducibility and encourage reuse for cross-country comparisons through the broader MeLiDos network.

Nonetheless, the dataset is quite small and demographically narrow ($n = 15$, mean age ≈ 22 years) which limits generalizability somewhat but this is an excellent start.

Minor methodological clarifications should be updated for the revision:

1. Wear/non-wear flagging methodology should be included and how this was handled in the resultant data.
2. Replication scripts for summary plots
3. Why not use the actiwatches for sleep timing/duration measurement/reporting and include in the dataset? Contemporaneous measurement can be very useful for analysis.

4. For the claim of this being the first work on this topic, perhaps include a database search reference (date; terms)

Overall, this work is a valuable contribution to global circadian and environmental health research. It bridges a major geographic gap in personal light exposure data and provides a robust framework for future comparative and mechanistic studies.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sleep, circadian rhythms, genetics, actigraphy, epidemiology, statistics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 14 October 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23041.r61413>

© 2025 Ribeiro da Silva Vallim J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Julia Ribeiro da Silva Vallim

Universidade Federal de São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil

Summary of the Article

The data note under review is a valuable and novel investigation of real-life light exposure patterns in a specific demographic and geographic context: residents of Kumasi, Ghana. The authors supplement objective light logger data with subjective measures of sleep, light perception, and mood, resulting in a comprehensive and distinctive dataset. The thorough dataset description includes group- and individual-level data that are well-presented and informative. The study's novelty and its potential to serve as a reference for future work in this field are clear strengths.

Overall Evaluation

The authors successfully addressed most of my concerns as a reviewer. The procedures and data presentation are sound and meaningfully contribute to the scientific literature. One key methodological aspect, however, requires clarification to ensure the article's scientific rigor and reproducibility.

1. Clarification of "Normal Vision" Eligibility Criteria

The authors state that participants were required to have "normal vision," but they do not define this term. Was it based on a previous diagnosis? Or was it based on self-reporting of no ocular diseases? Do the criteria for "normal" vision differ between younger and older adults?

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sleep and Circadian Medicine

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.
